

Improved Analytical Methods for Offshore Pile Foundations in the Caspian Sea under Environmental and Operational Dynamic Loads

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Abstract. Offshore pile foundations in the Azerbaijani sector of the Caspian Sea face complex environmental, geotechnical, and operational challenges. Long-term marine exposure causes corrosion, reducing structural reliability and load-bearing capacity. Dynamic loads from rotating machinery in gas turbine plants and compressor stations induce vibrations affecting serviceability and safety, in addition to static effects governing settlement and capacity. A unified approach addressing both static and dynamic responses is essential for reliable foundation design.

This study presents an integrated experimental, numerical, and analytical framework to evaluate axial load-bearing capacity, settlement behavior, and vibration response of thin-walled tubular piles. Pile-soil interaction is modeled using nonlinear continuum mechanics, with soil represented as an elasto-plastic heterogeneous medium governed by plastic flow theory with hardening, while the pile is assumed elastic. A displacement-based axisymmetric finite element model is used for static analysis, incorporating dynamic effects through machinery operational characteristics. Nonlinear governing equations are solved via an incremental–iterative scheme with Cholesky decomposition. Validation against full-scale static load tests shows measured load-settlement curves closely match numerical predictions.

The results demonstrate that this methodology provides a robust tool for analysis, design, and retrofitting of offshore pile foundations, improving predictions for static and dynamic performance and enhancing offshore infrastructure reliability.

Keywords: Caspian Sea offshore structures, offshore pile foundations, deep pile foundations, natural frequency of oscillations, machine-induced vibration

INTRODUCTION

The strategic development of hydrocarbon resources in the Caspian Sea region necessitates the deployment of a wide range of offshore infrastructure. These engineering structures are critical for accommodating process equipment, operational personnel, and the full spectrum of production workflows. Collectively referred to as offshore oil facilities (OOFs), such structures are typically constructed using prefabricated modular technologies and are implemented in the form of artificial island bases, trestle systems, and clustered platforms, each serving specific technological functions. The arrangement and integration of these components along trestle corridors ensure operational continuity and safety in complex marine environments. The design and implementation of OOFs demand a multidisciplinary approach, encompassing structural engineering, marine construction, and environmental safety, particularly within the challenging geotechnical and hydrometeorological conditions of the Caspian basin.

The foundational systems of offshore oil facilities in the Caspian Sea are primarily based on bored-and-filled pile technologies, including composite piles that integrate a steel casing with an internal anchoring system. These anchors are typically composed of one or more concentrically positioned steel pipes, structurally connected via radial spacers. To ensure monolithic behavior and corrosion resistance, the internal volume of the anchor- as well as the annular gap between the casing and the anchor-is completely filled with cementitious grout of fluid consistency. These substructures are subjected to complex loading conditions, including significant horizontal forces induced by wave dynamics and wind pressure, as well as substantial vertical loads resulting from

the self-weight of the platform, installed technological systems, and heavy drilling infrastructure, such as a 53-meter-high drilling rig. The design of these support systems must therefore meet high standards of geotechnical reliability and structural stability under dynamic marine conditions.

The stability, load-bearing capacity, and long-term durability of hydraulic engineering structures—such as berths, offshore platforms, pier systems, and coastal installations—play a critical role in the sustainable development of oil and gas infrastructure in the Caspian Sea. These structures are analyzed in accordance with contemporary engineering standards, which necessitate a comprehensive assessment of environmental and operational loads. In addition to dynamic impacts from wind, wave action, sea currents, and seismic activity, particular attention is paid to vertical loads, which arise from the operational use of these facilities. These include static and impact forces associated with heavy drilling equipment, superstructures (e.g., residential and utility blocks), as well as the live and dead loads of materials and machinery stationed on the platform deck. The accurate modeling of these combined effects is essential for ensuring the structural integrity and operational safety of hydraulic facilities throughout their service life.

In recent years, significant attention has been devoted to the analysis and modeling of pile foundations under complex loading and soil interaction conditions. Studies utilizing the three-dimensional finite element method (3D FEM) have explored the effects of lateral loads, pile-soil interaction, and boundary conditions on the structural behavior of piles (Abo-Youssef et al., 2021). Research has also focused on determining the ultimate bearing capacity of piles based on the torsional moments developed during pile installation (Alekseev and Bezzolev, 2023) and on the formulation of predictive models for pile performance (Alzabeebee et al., 2024). Parametric investigations into helical piles, including variables such as embedment depth, friction angle, helix-to-shaft diameter ratio, number of spirals, and spacing between them, have also been conducted using FEM approaches (Angurana et al., 2024).

Advanced computational techniques, such as the adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) optimized via the imperialist competitive algorithm, have been applied to predict pile bearing capacity with improved accuracy (Armaghani et al., 2022). In the context of offshore structures, studies have examined the stress–strain behavior of hydraulic facilities under both permanent and transient loading scenarios (Aslanov, 2015a, 2015b, 2016, 2022; Aslanov and Aslanli, 2024a–c; Aslanov and Aslanov, 2024a, 2024b, 2025; Aslanov et al., 2024–2026), emphasizing the critical role of environmental loading in design assessments.

Other researchers have addressed the heterogeneity of the soil foundation, proposing refined models such as elastic layers resting on elastic half-spaces for more accurate settlement predictions (Bokov and Fedorovskii, 2021). Laboratory investigations using reinforced sand beds with jute geotextiles (Burağadda and Orekanti, 2024) and elastoplastic analyses of shallow foundations incorporating Winkler-type soil models (Campione, 2024) further contribute to the understanding of foundation behavior under realistic conditions.

Additional studies have developed higher-order shear deformation theories for analyzing the buckling of porous, functionally graded sandwich plates on Winkler–Pasternak foundations (Chaabani et al., 2022), while machine learning models enhanced with optimization algorithms have been applied for predicting geotechnical parameters (Chen and Chen, 2024). Torsional vibration analysis of cylindrical foundations embedded in soil layers (Chen et al., 2023), FEM-based evaluations of foundation systems including pile groups and pile slabs (Chimdesa et al., 2023), and in-situ field testing of test piles (Dohyun, 2025) have provided valuable empirical and analytical data.

Finally, the settlement behavior of homogeneous foundations using integral estimation methods (Dubrakova et al., 2023) and the 3D numerical modeling of pile groups under lateral loading in sandy soils (Elgridly et al., 2022) further illustrate the diversity and depth of current research in this domain.

Recent investigations have examined the performance of various pile configurations under diverse geotechnical and environmental conditions. For instance, Fattah et al. (2024) analyzed the load distribution between the shaft and tip of pile groups tested in both saturated and unsaturated

soils with differing properties. In a large-scale in-situ testing campaign, Feng et al. (2024) evaluated the structural response of piles embedded in sand, loess, and layered soil profiles under variable loading conditions, while Gang (2024) further contributed to the field assessment of pile foundations in multi-layered strata.

Gotman and Evdokimov (2023) introduced a numerical approach for analyzing pile foundations of bridge abutments affected by karstic deformations, incorporating the influence of negative skin friction along the pile shaft. In the domain of geophysical site characterization, Hadi et al. (2024) employed seismic and geotechnical parameters—including depth, wave velocity, Young's modulus, shear modulus, and Poisson's ratio—to classify subsurface zones based on their mechanical behavior. The deflection of metal elements has been calculated using a three-line strain diagram by Hajiyev et al. (2024).

Han et al. (2024) conducted a comparative assessment of permeable and impermeable concrete piles, focusing on settlement, bearing capacity, axial forces, and skin friction characteristics. Hassona and Hakeem (2024) evaluated the performance of traditional concrete piles relative to polyurethane-based piles in both clayey and sandy soils, emphasizing differences in bearing efficiency.

The study by He et al. (2023) utilized finite element analysis to define the failure envelope of octagonal foundations under undrained conditions at zero interface stress, while another study (He et al., 2022) compared two bottom-lifting pile types to assess their behavior in layered foundation soils. Heidarie Golafzani et al. (2022) reviewed various methods—static analysis, in-situ load testing, dynamic testing, and numerical modeling—for estimating the axial bearing capacity of piles.

Hoang and Thanh (2024) investigated the vibrational characteristics of composite plates resting on inhomogeneous elastic foundations and immersed in fluid environments, with reinforcement through functionally graded graphene. Huded and Dash (2024) explored the behavior of pile end supports in stratified soil profiles affected by liquefaction and non-liquefaction conditions, contributing to better understanding of pile-soil interaction under seismic and hydraulic influences. The study conducted by Iskandarov et al. (2024) analyzes the hydrodynamic loads on pipeline systems and the structural changes in multifaceted gas pipelines.

Recent advancements in foundation engineering have included a broad spectrum of analytical, experimental, and numerical studies addressing the behavior and optimization of pile systems under various geotechnical conditions. Jassim et al. (2022) presented a detailed parametric study on the optimal geometric configuration of truncated cone-shaped containers, contributing to structural optimization under load. Jin et al. (2022) conducted static and combined load tests using a practical model with sixteen piles in sandy soils to investigate the performance of pile groups under complex load interactions.

Kalinin et al. (2022) proposed methodologies for deriving the soil deformation modulus from punch test results, while KangIL et al. (2024) explored the installation techniques and load-bearing behavior of micropile rafts. Kong et al. (2023) examined the impact of vertical compressive loading on molded pile systems, enhancing understanding of axial capacity in cohesionless soils.

In the field of computational modeling, Kumar et al. (2024) compared the predictive capabilities of several deep learning architectures—including DNN, CNN, RNN, LSTM, and Bidirectional algorithms—for analyzing dynamic pile load datasets. Lai et al. (2022) developed axisymmetric finite element models to evaluate the bearing capacity of ring foundations in anisotropic and heterogeneous clays, while Magade and Ingle (2021) reviewed traditional and contemporary approaches for pile design.

Mahmood et al. (2022) identified the most reliable interpretation methods for cast-in-place piles, and Majumder and Chakraborty (2021) employed 3D numerical modeling to assess the lateral response of underexpanded piles embedded in clayey soils. Maralapalle and Hegde (2024) investigated pile-soil-rock interactions through load tests to quantify surface friction and base resistance.

Mellal et al. (2023) applied a three-variable higher-order shear deformation theory to analyze

the vibrational and stability characteristics of functionally graded beams on variable elastic foundations. Subsurface interaction effects-particularly those induced by tunneling near pile elements have been addressed by Mirsepahi et al. (2021) and Mukhtiar et al. (2025a, 2025b) through 3D simulations, considering spatial relationships near the pile shaft and toe.

Murali et al. (2022) utilized a miniature pile testing system to explore the load transfer mechanisms of socketed piles in synthetic soft rock, while Naeem et al. (2025) focused on the sequential influence of basement excavation and tunneling on adjacent single piles. Nguyen et al. (2024) proposed a hybrid machine learning model, combining genetic algorithms and neural networks for rapid evaluation of pile bearing capacity, and Pantelidis (2021) introduced a method based on the superposition principle in elasticity theory to calculate equivalent elastic constants for heterogeneous soil environments.

Recent research has increasingly leveraged advanced computational and remote sensing technologies to enhance the predictive accuracy of foundation behavior under diverse geotechnical conditions. For example, Pham et al. (2022) utilized deep neural networks to estimate the axial load-carrying capacity of piles, while Shen (2024) applied machine learning techniques for the reliable prediction of pile bearing performance. Roohi et al. (2021) employed Sentinel-1 satellite imagery processed via SNAP software to evaluate ground settlement dynamics, highlighting the role of geospatial data in monitoring subsurface behavior. Sharafutdinov et al. (2024) proposed a model for settlement prediction of single bored piles that incorporates elastoplastic soil behavior, thereby offering greater realism in deformation assessment.

In the study by Shubham et al. (2024), a comprehensive PLAXIS 2D simulation was conducted using eight parametric variations to estimate the settlement of shallow foundations situated above circular cavities. Sidorov and Le (2024) comparatively analyzed the key features and input parameters of three distinct soil models, contributing to model selection strategies in numerical geotechnics. Singh et al. (2022) examined the mechanical behavior of rock masses under strip foundation loading, while Sofiyev et al. (2022) analyzed the nonlinear vibrations of shallow shell structures placed on elastic foundations modeled using the Pasternak two-parameter model, relevant to anisotropic and heterogeneous conditions.

Feedback-based neural network models were developed by Swarnkar et al. (2024) for improved performance in geotechnical prediction tasks. Experimental insights were provided by Verumandy et al. (2024) through static load tests on grooved piles at four different construction sites, and by Wenshuai et al. (2024), who studied the horizontal load behavior of rectangular piles before and after concrete casting.

Foundation-structure interaction under seismic influences was analyzed by Wibowo et al. (2024), focusing on the effects of soil type and differential settlement on reinforced concrete buildings. Wu et al. (2024a) investigated the non-uniform compressive modulus gradients in unsaturated soils, specifically analyzing how the stiffness of soil particles and skeleton vary with depth in roadway subgrades. In a complementary study, Wu et al. (2024b) explored the dynamic response of roadbeds under uniform traffic loading, taking into account the inhomogeneous mechanical properties of unsaturated soil layers.

Finally, Xiao and Du (2024) introduced a hybrid AI-based approach combining radial basis function networks and multilayer perceptrons, optimized via an arithmetic optimization algorithm, to evaluate the bearing capacity of driven piles using a curated experimental dataset-demonstrating the growing role of artificial intelligence in geotechnical analysis.

Recent efforts in geotechnical modeling have expanded to include advanced machine learning and probabilistic approaches for the evaluation of complex soil-structure systems. Yaychi and Esmaeili-Falak (2024) explored the effectiveness of tree-based algorithms for predicting the axial load capacity of piles, highlighting their potential for use in data-driven foundation design. Yuan et al. (2024) investigated the influence of spatial variability in soil properties on the bearing behavior of rigid foundations subjected to large deformations, emphasizing the need to incorporate stochastic soil characteristics into design frameworks.

Zhang and Dieudonné (2023) introduced a uniform carbonate distribution model to capture

the effects of heterogeneity on biocemented soils, utilizing the discrete element method (DEM) to simulate the mechanical response of samples with varying internal structures. Their findings contribute to the understanding of bio-mediated soil improvement techniques. In parallel, Zhao et al. (2024) developed a concrete–rock shear interaction model, grounded in statistical theory, which accounts for the random distribution patterns of rock fragmentation, enabling more realistic predictions in jointed rock masses.

Zhu and Zhu (2022) proposed a comprehensive framework for analyzing building settlement behavior by combining the Gaussian distribution law for ground variability with the equivalent beam method, which incorporates bending and shear deformation of the structure, residual soil deformation, and the potential for detachment between the building and the ground. Their study elucidated the complex interdependence between building load, settlement, and the number of storeys, offering practical insights into urban geotechnics and differential settlement risk.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research was conducted using a rigorous mathematical framework and well-established principles of structural mechanics, as commonly applied in the analysis and design of hydraulic and offshore engineering structures. The primary aim was to investigate the vibrational behavior of pile foundations beneath marine facilities located on continental shelf soils—an essential consideration for the accurate analysis and safe design of offshore platforms.

Design decisions were informed by a comprehensive assessment of site-specific parameters, including technological constraints, applied design loads, as well as engineering-geological and hydrogeological characteristics of the selected marine area.

A unified research program was implemented, combining both experimental field data and theoretical analysis to develop scientifically grounded engineering methods for evaluating wave-induced loads on open-frame offshore oil and gas production platforms. A novel calculation approach was formulated based on the outcomes of these investigations.

Numerical simulations were carried out using specialized structural analysis software tools, including **SACS 5.5 8Vi (Structural Analysis Computer System)** and **STAAD.Pro V8i**, to validate theoretical models and support the development of improved engineering calculation techniques.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Pile Foundation Vibrations and Dynamic Response Analysis

One of the most significant tasks of rational and economic design of rod-type spatial marine hydraulic structures is the task of determining the loads acting on them.

Due to the absence of vibration in the gas turbine of the Gas Turbine Thermal Power Plant (GTTPP), measurement and research work was carried out and the results were analyzed. The purpose of the conducted research is to select a reasonable foundation design to prevent vibration in the generator control unit during operation of the gas turbine generator. GTTPP is an industrial enterprise that produces both electricity and heat and is the source of electricity and heat supply for all industrial and domestic consumers in the Oil Rocks and Gunashli fields of Azerbaijan.

This is an autonomous power plant that does not have a single connection to the external network. Depending on the ambient temperature, the total capacity of the station is between 45 ÷ 48 MW. The main equipment of the GTTPP is six gas turbine generators. Of these, four turbines operate on gas fuel, and two turbines, dual-fuel, operate on gas and diesel fuel. 25% of the compressed air in a gas turbine engine is used for combustion, and 75% for cooling the power turbine. The gas turbine generator set consists of a gas turbine engine, generator, gearbox, turbine and generator control system, starting system, fuel system and lubrication system.

In the conducted studies, strong vibration occurred in the generator control unit at 30÷35%,

75–82% and certain readings of the device after loading. On the part of the site where the generators are located, 6 foundations of 11x3 m in size, completely isolated from the site structure, each of which consists of 8 piles, are designed for these devices. The transverse and longitudinal stability of the structure is ensured by connections consisting of pipes $\varnothing 219 \times 10$, $\varnothing 219 \times 12$ mm and 60 I-beams B1, connecting the support piles to each other at a slope of 5:1. Under the power units, the piles are fixed with a 4 m deep pile from the lower end. The internal cavity of the pile $\varnothing 530 \times 12$ mm is reinforced with a perforated anchor pile $\varnothing 426 \times 11$ mm at a distance of 15 m from the upper end and filled with cement mortar. A monolithic reinforced concrete unit is created for the joint operation of reinforced concrete anchor piles and beams at the joints of the beams and piles. In the water area where the site is designed, the sea bottom is quite flat. The water depth under the site varies from 5.9 to 6.1 m from north to south. The distance from the floor of the site to the calm sea level is 5.0 meters. According to the physical and mechanical properties, the soil mainly consists of sand, dust and clay. To study the relief of the seabed, the sizes of underwater and above-water obstacles and their locations, as well as the sediments of the seabed in the gravitational zone of the water area with a depth of up to 20 m, the results of bathymetric, hydrolocation and hydrogeological studies were used.

The facility is located in the southwestern part of the existing gas turbine power plant in the Oil Rocks area, 37 km east of the Absheron Peninsula. The water area where the facility is located is surrounded by a berth bridge to the north and by the existing gas turbine power plant to the east. There are power transmission lines, water pipes, oil and gas pipelines in the area. The meridional length of the Caspian Sea from north to south and its location in different climatic zones determine changes in the temperature regime of the air and water. The air temperature in the Oil Rocks water area of the Caspian Sea varies. In the Oil Rocks water area, the highest air temperature of -28.7°C was observed in August, and in February -3.1°C (6.1°C). The average annual water temperature fluctuates between $15-16.9^{\circ}\text{C}$. The average long-term water temperature is 15.9°C . The long-term absolute maximum and minimum water temperatures are 32°C and 3.5°C , respectively.

The values of long-term wind data for the recent period were collected and analyzed in the water area of Oil Rocks. As can be seen from the table, in the water area recorded in winter, northerly winds prevail by 23%. The frequency of southerly winds is 12-16%, northwesterly winds 14%, easterly and westerly winds 6%. In the spring season, the frequency of northerly (27%), northwesterly (21%), southerly (14%), southeasterly (12%) winds usually prevail. The frequency of winds of other directions is 7%. Mainly northerly (42%), northwesterly (22%), northeasterly (21%) winds prevail. In autumn, as in winter, the frequency of winds of all directions fluctuates within 11-27%, with the exception of westerly (2%) and southwesterly (7%). The frequency of wind speed gradations by direction is shown in Fig. 1.

If we compare the recurrence by wind directions in the Oil Rocks water area, we will see that the recurrence of northern and north-western winds is 29% and 18%, respectively. The recurrence of winds of other directions fluctuates within 4-12%. The average annual number of calm days in the Oil Rocks water area is 6 days. The recurrence of the gradation of various wind speeds in the northern, north-western, north-eastern and south-eastern directions is 12%, 7.7%, 6.3% and 4.9%, respectively. Gusts of wind with a speed of 16-20 m/s usually spread in the northern (1.6%) and north-western (1.4%) direction. Winds with a speed of more than 25 m/s are also common, as are northern and north-western directions (0.021% v \varnothing 0.01%). Maximum wind speeds (18, 24, 28 and 40 m/s) are mainly observed during winds from the north. During southern winds, the maximum wind speed fluctuates within 10-16 m/s. In almost all months of the year, northern, north-eastern gusts of wind with a speed of 20-40 m/s are observed. Also, north-north-eastern (14-24 m/s), east-north-eastern (14-24 m/s), north-western (8-16 m/s) and north-north-

western (7-18 m/s) winds also have high speed by month throughout the year.

Fig.1. Seasonal wind direction changes in the Oil Rocks field of the Caspian Sea.

In fig. 1 the following notations are introduced:

North (N), North – East (NE), East (E), South – East (SE), South (S), South – West (SW), West (W), North – West (NW)

Since the beginning of oil production, the study of wind and wave regime has been intensively developed. The available observational materials still allow us to determine the sizes of wave elements and the patterns between them, on the shelf and in the open sea. Long-term values of wave data for the last period have been collected and analyzed. Waves of 4.6-7.0 m in height are observed only with northern and north-western winds, the frequency of which is 0.1-0.4% and 0.02-0.1%, respectively. Waves of 8-9 m in height occur only with a northern wind, their frequency fluctuates within 0.01-0.03%. As can be seen from the repetition of gradations in the directions of wave heights, the repetition of waves with a height of 0.6-1.0; 1.1-1.5 and 0.1-0.5 m in the northern direction is greater than the repetition of wave heights in other directions and is 8.8; 7.2; 5.9%, respectively.

In the summary of wind and wave loads in the design and operation of offshore hydraulic oil field equipment, the seasonal distribution of wave elements is calculated, which can be observed once in 1.5, 10, 20, 50 and 100 years. The average height of the calculated waves observed once in 100 years in winter and autumn (4.8 and 5.2 m) is higher than in other seasons. It fluctuates within 141-189 m. If we compare the seasonal variation in wave height with a guarantee of 1 and 0.1%, we can see that the possible wave height once in 100 years in autumn and winter, respectively, is 12.5; 11.5 m and 14.6; 13.4 m. For a depth of 6 m, different values of wave elements of the frequently repeating northwest wind are calculated (Fig. 2).

Seasonal changes in the level are determined by the ratio of the tidal and ebb parts of the water balance, which changes the sea level to varying degrees depending on the physical and geographical conditions of a given region. The change in the level is distinguished by its diversity in different points and reflects the general average pattern for the sea as a whole. Fluctuations in the tide level are associated with the variability of the tidal parts of the water balance elements. These factors are manifested in the seasonal ebb of the level in a particular area of the sea. During the year, the lowest level is observed in December and February. The level begins to rise in March-July, but the most intense increase is observed in May-June. The highest level is in June-July,

which is associated with the spring flood in these rivers. A decrease in river water flow and an increase in evaporation from the sea surface in July-August lead to a gradual decrease in the sea level to the winter minimum. Sometimes in December-January there is a slight rise in the water level, which is replaced by a slight rise in February (1-3 cm).

If the piles are taken as a rigid stamp with a flat circular base located on an elastic shelf half-space, which are acted upon by a vertical force $Q+P$ (where Q and P are constant loads) directed along the axis of symmetry. Under the action of these loads, the pile will perform, like a rigid stamp, harmonic oscillations with an amplitude of A_0 relative to the position of static equilibrium. We assume that the separation of the pile (stamp) from the elastic half-space (shelf soil) does not occur. The friction forces between the piles and the elastic half-space (shelf soil) are not taken into account. There is no load on the half-space outside the pile (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Directional variation of wave height in the Oil Rocks field of the Caspian Sea

In fig.2 the following notations are introduced:

North (N), North - North - East (NNE), North - East (NE), East - North - East (ENE), East (E), East - South - East (ESE), South - East (SE), South - South - East (SSE), South (S), South - South - West (SSW), South - West (SW), West - South - West (WSW), West (W), West - North - West (WNW), North - West (NW), North - North - West (NNW).

Fig. 3. Vibrations of a pile foundation under an offshore structure due to the action of a vertical disturbing force with a round base made of shelf soils.

We accept the movements of the pile (stamp) in the following form:

$$W(t) = W_{sm}^Q + A_0 e^{i(\omega t - \theta)}, \quad (1)$$

where $W(t)$ is the total vertical displacement of the pile (stamp), measured from the unloaded state; W_{st}^Q – static displacement of the pile due to force Q (constant load); A_0 – amplitude of pile vibrations; θ – is the phase shift angle between the displacement of the pile (stamp) and the disturbing force; ω is the angular frequency of oscillations.

At the same time

$$W_{sm}^Q = \frac{Q}{8(1-\psi^2)GR}; \quad \psi = \left(\frac{G}{\lambda+2G}\right)^{1/2}; \quad (2)$$

where $\lambda = \frac{E\mu_0}{(1+\mu_0)(1-2\mu_0)}$ and G are the Lamé elastic constants, G is the shear modulus; μ_0 – Poisson's ratio of shelf soil; R – radius of the base under the pile sole.

The amplitude of harmonic oscillations can be determined by the formula:

$$A_0 = K_d W_{cm}^P; \quad \text{tg } \theta = \frac{\sin \delta}{\cos \delta - \xi}, \quad (3)$$

Here K_d is the dynamic coefficient for displacements determined by:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} K_d &= \frac{1}{\gamma_0(1-2\xi \cos \delta + \xi^2)^2}; \quad \xi = \frac{\eta^2 m_1}{8(1-\psi^2)\gamma_0}; \\ \eta &= \omega R \left(\frac{\rho}{G}\right)^{1/2}; \quad m_1 = \frac{m}{\rho R^3}. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

W_{sm}^P – is determined by formula (2) with Q replaced by P ; ρ is the density of the shelf soil in the half-space; m is the mass of the pile (stamp).

We assume that there will be no separation of the pile from the soil of the elastic soil foundation in the half-space if $W_{sm}^Q > A_0$.

Formulas (3), (4) include the values of γ_0 and δ . Table 1 shows the values of γ_0 and δ for some Poisson's ratios μ_0 of shelf soil and the parameter η . Using formulas (3), (4) and Table 1, we determine the amplitude of oscillations A_0 of the pile (stamp) and the phase shift angle θ .

Table 1.

Values of γ_0 and δ from μ_0 and η .

η	γ_0 at value μ_0			δ при значении μ_0		
	0,00	0,25	0,50	0,00	0,25	0,50
0,00	1,0000	1,0000	1,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000
0,25	1,0139	1,0121	1,0097	0,2135	0,1968	0,2079
0,50	1,0579	1,0498	1,0402	0,4235	0,3908	0,4141
0,75	1,1380	1,1177	1,0948	0,6243	0,5774	0,6152

1,00	1,2608	1,2186	1,1776	0,8072	0,7626	0,8061
1,25	1,4319	1,3646	1,2917	0,9627	0,9005	0,9812
1,50	1,6467	1,5469	1,4515	1,0885	1,0239	1,1166

Using (4) and Table 1, one can graphically plot the changes in the dynamic coefficient K_d depending on η for fixed values of μ_0 and m_1 . Fig. 4 shows graphs for the case and $m_1 = 0,5,10,20$.

Fig. 4. Graph of the dependence of K_d on η for $m_1 = 0,5,10,20$, for $\mu_0 = 0,25$.

Fig. 5. Graph of the dependence of θ on η for $m_1 = 0,5,10,20$, for $\mu_0 = 0,25$.

Fig. 5 shows the change in phase angle θ depending on η for $\mu_0 = 0,25$ and $m_1 = 0,5,10,20$. The total static and dynamic normal stresses σ_z at the contact area under the pile base and the soil foundation from offshore structures can be determined by the following formula:

$$\sigma_z(r, 0, t) = \sigma_{z(cm.)}^Q(r, 0) + \sigma_{z(cm.)}^P(r, 0)\alpha(r)e^{i[\omega t - \Phi(r)]}, (0 \leq r \leq R); \quad (5)$$

where

$$\sigma_{z(cm.)}^Q(r, 0) = -\frac{q}{2\pi R(R^2 - r^2)^{1/2}}, (0 \leq r \leq R); \quad (6)$$

$$\alpha(r)e^{-i\Phi(r)} = \frac{1}{\gamma_0(1 - 2\xi \cos \delta + \xi^2)^{1/2}} \cdot \left[p(1) - \left(1 - \frac{r^2}{R^2}\right) \sum_{n=0}^N \alpha_n \cdot \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^{2n} \right]. \quad (7)$$

The expression for $\sigma_{z(cm)}^P(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{0})$ can be obtained from (6) by replacing \mathbf{Q} with \mathbf{P} . In the case when the force $\mathbf{Q} + \mathbf{P} \cos \omega t$ acts on the piles (stamp), in formula (5) $e^{i[\omega t - \Phi(\mathbf{r})]}$ should be replaced by $\cos[\omega t - \Phi(\mathbf{r})]$. Here $\sigma_{z(cm)}^P(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{0})$ is the normal stress at the contact area between the pile base and the shelf soil foundation under static application of force \mathbf{P} ; $\alpha(\mathbf{r})$ – dynamic coefficient for stress σ_z ; $\Phi(\mathbf{r})$ is the phase shift angle between the voltage and the applied force. Table 2 shows the values of the complex numbers α_n (for $N=4$) and $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{1})$ for the case $\mu_0 = 0,25$, with the upper rows showing the values of the real part of the number α_n and $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{1})$, and the lower rows showing the values of the imaginary part.

Table 2.

Values of $\alpha(i)$ and $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{1})$ from η .

η	α_0	α_1	α_2	α_3	α_4	$\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{1})$
0,00	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	1,0000
	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000	0,0000
0,25	0,0468	0,0001	-0,0001	0,0007	-0,0013	1,0079
	-0,0026	-0,0003	0,0034	-0,0171	0,0189	0,1971
0,50	0,1872	-0,0006	-0,0186	0,0683	-0,0588	1,323
	-0,0212	0,0012	-0,0105	0,0336	-0,0275	0,3930
0,75	0,4202	-0,0066	-0,0082	0,0189	-0,0122	1,0742
	-0,0741	0,0010	0,0095	-0,0220	0,0152	0,58591
1,00	0,7345	0,0155	-1,0701	3,7443	-3,1036	1,1290
	-0,1738	-0,0383	1,3073	-4,5654	3,7816	0,77661
1,25	1,1419	-0,0902	0,6395	-2,3336	2,0152	1,2166
	-0,3760	0,0614	-0,5244	1,9128	-1,6525	0,9501
1,50	1,5950	-0,0931	-0,4291	1,5936	-1,3966	1,3159
	-0,6808	0,1025	-0,3660	1,3351	-1,1874	1,1066

For clarity, Figure 7 illustrates the dependence of the dynamic coefficient α_0 on the parameter m_1 , while maintaining a constant value of $\mu_0 = 0.25$. The selected range of m_1 values (0.5, 10, and 20) enables a comprehensive evaluation of the system's dynamic sensitivity over a broad spectrum of stiffness and mass ratios.

The pile foundation system is subjected to vertically acting excitation forces resulting from the combined influence of the self-weight of marine surface structures, operational loads induced by onboard equipment, and hydrodynamic forces generated by wave action. These loading components collectively produce both static and dynamic effects within the soil medium.

Based on the adopted analytical framework, the resulting stress state within the soil underlying the circular foundations was evaluated by considering the superposition of static and dynamic stress components. Particular attention was given to the interaction between the imposed dynamic loads and the deformational response of the soil mass.

The results reveal the distribution characteristics of stresses in the foundation soil and emphasize the significance of soil–structure interaction effects under combined loading conditions. These findings are of critical importance for the reliable design and safety assessment of offshore foundation systems, particularly in environments subjected to intense dynamic excitation.

Fig.6. Graph of the dependence of $\alpha(0)$ on η for $m_l=0,5,10,12$, for $\mu_0 = 0,25$.

3.2. Calculation of pile bearing capacity under dynamic loading

In this paper, the problem is solved using the following calculation model. The pile (1) is subjected to a force arising from the operation of equipment and machines Fig. 7. Under the action of this force, the pile, vibrating, overcomes the friction developing along the lateral surfaces in the presence of elastic connections (2), characterizing the elasticity of the soil. The connections (2) connect the pile to the runners (5). Let us assume that between the lateral surfaces of the pile and the soil there is only dry friction, the magnitude of which does not depend on the vibration of the pile. Overcoming the friction developing along the lateral surfaces, the pile vibrates and hits the plug (3), which descends if the force applied to it exceeds the value of the soil resistance.

Fig. 7. Calculation model of bearing capacity of piles: 1- pile; 2,4- elastic connections; 3- cork; 5- runners

To communicate to a pile of length (l) a movement at a speed v in the ground, it is necessary to expend power W . Under this condition, the equilibrium equation can be written as

$$(N - P)v = W, \quad (8)$$

Where N is the load supported by the pile, or the bearing capacity; P – total mass of pile, equipment and machines.

When the pile vibrates, the surrounding soil, due to its inertial properties, creates additional added mass along the entire length of the pile. This added mass – the runners (5) – when the pile moves, they move together with it or slide along its surface. When the pile is displaced, the runners (5) move together with it until the elastic force of the connections (2) and (4) reaches the value of friction Q_{tr} and end resistance Q_{tor} . In this case, the region in which the values of Q_{tr} and Q_{tor} have reached their limiting values is of particular interest. To compile the equation of dynamic equilibrium of the runner (5), we will consider its rod connected to the mass of the pile in the presence of friction force and end resistance of the soil. Then the equation describing the longitudinal vibrations of elastic runners can be represented as

$$\left(EF + \tau u + \frac{u\sigma}{4l} \right) \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial x^2} = -m_0 \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial t^2} - P(x, t), \quad (9)$$

where EF is the rigidity of the runners; u – pile perimeter taking into account runners; τ – friction force per unit length of the pile between the soil and the runners; l – length of pile in the ground ; σ – soil resistance under the end of the pile; m_0 - pile mass per unit length; $P(x, t)$ – inertial load of the soil acting on the pile.

$$P(x, t) = \alpha_0 \frac{D\gamma u_0}{2g} \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial t^2} \quad (10)$$

where D, u_0 is the diameter and perimeter of the cross-section of the pile; γ is the soil density; g – acceleration due to gravity; α_0 is a coefficient which for the case under consideration is taken to be equal to $\alpha_0 = 1$.

$$\text{Then } \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial t^2} = \frac{a^2}{\alpha} \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial x^2}; \quad (11)$$

$$a^2 = \frac{EF + \tau u + \frac{u\sigma}{4l}}{m_0}; \quad \alpha = 1 + \frac{Du_0\gamma}{2gm_0} \quad (12)$$

From equation (11) it is evident that the propagation speed of the elastic deformation wave during oscillation depends on the value of α (with increasing α the propagation speed of the elastic deformation wave decreases). Consequently, to impart movement to the pile, it is necessary to expend power α times greater than the power determined by formula (8). Based on formula (8), taking into account the above, we determine the bearing capacity of the pile under dynamic impact conditions

$$N = \alpha \frac{W}{v} + P, \quad (13)$$

Let us represent the power expended by the vibrator and the speed of movement of the pile through the amplitude a_0 , the frequency of oscillations ω and the acting forces of friction Q_{tr} and end resistance Q_{tor} :

$$W = \frac{4Q_{tr}a_0\omega}{2\pi} + Q_{top}a_0\omega; \quad v = a_0\omega \quad (14)$$

Then, based on (6), we obtain

$$N = \frac{2}{\pi} \left(1 + \frac{Du_0\gamma}{2gm_0} \right) Q_{tr} + \left(1 + \frac{Du_0\gamma}{2gm_0} \right) Q_{tor} + P \quad (15)$$

As can be seen from formula (15), the load-bearing capacity of a pile under dynamic loads is not affected by the dynamic parameters of the type of equipment and machines. It depends on the soil density, geometric dimensions and weight of the pile. In this case, it is necessary to achieve conditions under which the vibrator can create a source of vibration in the ground for the propagation of elastic waves. At the same time, it is necessary to limit the magnitude of these

vibrations, which contribute to the failure of the pile. The failure of a pile under the influence of a disturbing load in the presence of a static load will occur if

$$N < S + c\alpha_0, \quad (16)$$

where c is the total coefficient of rigidity of connections (3) and (4); α_0 – amplitude of longitudinal vibrations of the pile; N – static value of the bearing capacity of the pile.

The amplitudes of pile oscillations at the moment of failure can be represented as follows:

$$\alpha_0 = \frac{P_0}{c} \frac{1 - \alpha_m \frac{\omega^2}{\lambda^2}}{\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\lambda^2}\right)^2 + (\Phi\omega)^2}}; \quad (17)$$

$$\alpha_m = \frac{m}{M + \bar{m}} \quad (18)$$

where ω is the equipment oscillation frequency; λ - frequency of natural oscillations of the pile or (5); M – mass of pile equipment and machines; m – added mass of soil; \bar{m} – added mass of soil per unit length of pile.

$$\bar{m} = \frac{\alpha_0 \gamma D u_0}{2g} \quad (19)$$

Substituting expression (17) into inequality (16), we obtain:

$$N < \frac{\left(1 - \alpha_m \frac{\omega^2}{\lambda^2}\right) P_0}{\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\lambda^2}\right)^2 + (\Phi\omega)^2}} + S \quad (20)$$

In this formula, the desired value is λ . To determine λ , we return to equation (11), where the reduced mass of equipment and machines is taken as the mass m_0 . Then equation (11) will take the form.

$$\frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial t^2} = a^2 \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial x^2} \quad (21)$$

$$a^2 = \frac{EF + \tau u + \frac{u\sigma}{4l}}{\bar{M} + \bar{m}} \quad (22)$$

The general solution of equation (21) using the initial parameter method can be represented as

$$W(x, t) = \left(\gamma_0 \cos kx + \frac{\Delta_0}{k} \sin kx \right) \sin(\lambda t + \delta); \quad (23)$$

$$k^2 = \frac{\lambda^2}{a^2} = \frac{\lambda^2 (\bar{M} + \bar{m})}{EF + \tau u + \frac{u\sigma}{4l}} \quad (24)$$

where $\bar{M} + \bar{m}$ – respectively the reduced mass of equipment and machines and the attached mass of soil per unit length of the pile; γ_0 – initial displacement; Δ_0 – initial relative elongation.

Considering that equipment with a mass M_0 is attached to the pile, which in turn transfers the disturbing load to the runners, the movement of the upper end of the runners ($X=0$) will be imparted by a longitudinal force P equal to the inertial force of the equipment I_{ob} , i.e $P = I_{ob}$.

Knowing that the inertia force of the equipment $I_{ob} = M_0 \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial t^2}$, and replacing the longitudinal force P with relative elongation:

$$P = \Delta_0 \frac{\left(EF + \tau u + \frac{u\sigma}{4l}\right)}{l} = \frac{\partial W}{\partial x} \cdot \frac{\left(EF + \tau u + \frac{u\sigma}{4l}\right)}{l} \quad (25)$$

we get:

$$\frac{\left(EF + \tau u + \frac{u\sigma}{4l}\right)}{l} \cdot \frac{\partial W}{\partial x} = M_0 \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial t^2} \quad (26)$$

Determining the value of $\frac{\partial W}{\partial x}$ and $\frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial t^2}$ using equation (23) and substituting into condition (26), we find:

$$Y_0 = - \frac{\Delta_0 \left(EF + \tau u + \frac{u\sigma}{4l}\right)}{\lambda^2 M_0 l} \quad (27)$$

Considering that at the other end the relative elongation is zero $\left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial x} = 0\right)$, based on (23) we can write.

$$\Delta_0 = Y_0 k t g k l \quad (28)$$

After substituting the value γ_0 from (27) into (28), we obtain the equation

$$1 = - \frac{(EF + \tau u + \frac{u\sigma}{4l})k}{\lambda^2 M_0 l} t g k l \quad (29)$$

Replacing λ^2 from the formula ω (24), we obtain a frequency equation, which is solved by the trial and error method or the graphical method:

$$\frac{M}{M+m} k l = - t g k l \quad (30)$$

Taking the value

$$N = u \tau l + \frac{\pi D^2}{4} \sigma \quad (31)$$

and substituting the value of λ^2 from (24) into (20), we determine the pile failure condition:

$$\left[1 - \alpha_m \frac{\omega^2 (\bar{M} + \bar{m})}{k^2 (EF + \tau u + \frac{u\sigma}{4l})} \right] P_0 + \left[\sqrt{\left[1 - \frac{\omega^2 (\bar{M} + \bar{m})}{k^2 (EF + \tau u + \frac{u\sigma}{4l})} \right]^2 + (\Phi \omega)^2} \right] \times \left(S - u \tau l - \frac{\pi D^2}{4} \sigma \right) = 0 \quad (32)$$

In equation (32), the value of the friction force τ is sought. The failure condition will be met if the friction force τ is greater than the friction force τ_{kr} :

$$\tau > \tau_{kr} \quad (33)$$

Calculation formulas (15) and (32) are applicable to solid and hollow piles with a closed lower end operating under dynamic impact conditions and can also be used to determine the bearing capacity of these piles, driven equipment and machines. It was found that the density of the soil in the internal cavity of the pile slightly exceeds the density of the soil surrounding the pile. Therefore, the soil filling the internal cavity of the pile and surrounding it resists vertical compressive loads due to friction arising between the lateral surface of the soil core and the internal surface of the pile, and not due to the resistance of the end. Taking this into account, formulas (15) and (32) for determining the bearing capacity of piles operating under dynamic impact conditions can be reduced to the form

$$N = \frac{2}{\pi} \left(1 + \frac{D u_0 \gamma}{2 g m_0} \right) (Q_{tr}^v + Q_{tr}^n); \quad (34)$$

$$\left[1 - \alpha_m \frac{\omega^2 (\bar{M} + \bar{m})}{k^2 [EF + \tau(u_v + u_0)]} \right] P_0 + \left[\sqrt{\left\{ 1 - \frac{\omega^2 (\bar{M} + \bar{m})}{k^2 [EF + \tau(u_v + u_0)]} \right\}^2 + (\Phi \omega)^2} \right] \times [S - \tau l (u_v + u_0)] = 0 \quad (35)$$

Where u_v and u_0 are the perimeter of the internal cavity and the external surface of the pile, respectively; Q_{tr}^v and Q_{tr}^n are the total friction forces for the internal cavity and the external surface of the pile, respectively, which are considered to be given. If there is no data, the value of Q_{tr} is determined by the formula

$$Q_{tr} = u \gamma t g \varphi \frac{l^2}{2} \quad (36)$$

where φ is the angle of internal friction of the soil.

To verify the reliability of the proposed formulas, calculations were performed to determine the bearing capacity of hollow piles with an open lower end, immersed equipment and machines (see Table 3).

Table 3. Calculated and experimental data on the bearing capacity of piles.

Pile immersion depth, m	Soil density, t/m ³	Angle of internal friction φ , deg	Bearing capacity of pile, kN	
			Experimental significance	According to the proposed methodology
5,70	20,0	30	113,80	116,36
6,19	20,0	28	113,80	111,86
8,20	18,0	15	125,16	122,86
6,15	20,0	25	108,11	99,66
5,05	20,0	40	91,04	95,76

This study presents a computational methodology for evaluating the axial load-bearing capacity and settlement of thin-walled tubular piles subjected to vertical static loading. The pile-soil interaction is formulated within the framework of solid mechanics, where the computational domain is idealized as a piecewise homogeneous medium composed of multiple soil layers and the pile material. The overall system is thus treated as a deformable heterogeneous continuum, allowing for a consistent representation of the coupled mechanical response.

Taking into account the geometrical characteristics of the pile and the axial nature of loading, the problem is formulated under axisymmetric conditions. The governing boundary value problem is expressed in terms of the differential equations of plasticity theory. Within the pile, the stress–strain relationship is described by linear elasticity (Hooke’s law), whereas the surrounding soil is modeled using nonlinear constitutive relations derived from plastic flow theory with isotropic hardening. The plastic flow rule is defined according to Koiter’s associated flow rule:

$$d\varepsilon_{ij}^p = \sum_r d\lambda^r \frac{\partial f_r}{\partial \sigma_{ij}} \quad (37)$$

where ε_{ij}^p and σ_{ij} denote the components of the plastic strain tensor and the stress tensor, respectively, and $d\lambda^r \geq 0$ are scalar consistency parameters governed by loading conditions.

The yield surface is defined by a piecewise linear function consisting of three segments:

$$f_{r=1} = \sigma_1 - \sigma_{okt}(\omega_1) + \sigma \tan \varphi_{okt}(\omega_1) \quad (38)$$

$$f_{r=2} = \sigma_1 - [P_{okt}^*(\omega_1, \omega_v) + \sigma] \tan \psi_{okt}(\omega_1) \quad (39)$$

$$f_{r=3} = \sigma + P_{okt}(\omega_1, \omega_v) \quad (40)$$

The parameters defining the evolution of the yield surface are expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{okt}(\omega_1) &= \sigma_{okt}^0 + (\sigma_{okt}^* - \sigma_{okt}^0) f\left(\frac{\omega_1}{\omega_1^*}\right) \\ \tan \varphi_{okt}(\omega_1) &= \tan \varphi_{okt}^0 + (\tan \varphi_{okt}^* - \tan \varphi_{okt}^0) f\left(\frac{\omega_1}{\omega_1^*}\right) \\ P_{okt}(\omega_1, \omega_v) &= P_{okt} + \frac{(P_{okt} \tan \varphi_{okt}^* + \sigma_{okt}^*) f\left(\frac{\omega_1}{\omega_1^*}\right)}{f\left(\frac{\omega_v}{\omega_v^*}\right)} \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

Here, σ_{okt}^0 , φ_{okt}^0 , and ψ_{okt}^0 define the initial yield surface, while σ and σ_1 represent stress invariants.

To solve the resulting nonlinear system, the displacement-based finite element method is employed. The domain is discretized into axisymmetric toroidal elements obtained by revolving linear triangular elements about the axis of symmetry. Within each element, displacements are approximated using first-order polynomial interpolation functions.

The global system of equilibrium equations is expressed as:

$$[K]\{u\} = \{F\} \quad (42)$$

where $[K] = \sum_{e=1}^N [K^e]$ is the global stiffness matrix, $\{F\} = \sum_{e=1}^N \{F^e\}$ is the global force vector accounting for external loads, initial stresses, and strains, and $\{u\}$ is the vector of nodal displacements.

Boundary conditions are enforced through appropriate modification of the stiffness matrix. Owing to the symmetry and positive definiteness of $[K]$, the system is efficiently solved using the Cholesky decomposition method.

The nonlinear solution procedure is based on an incremental-iterative algorithm that accounts for the evolution of plastic deformation. At each load step, the total strain is decomposed into elastic and plastic components. Assuming that at step $t - 1$, the displacement, total strain, and plastic strain fields are known, the updated displacement vector at step t is obtained from:

$$[K]\{u\}_t = \{F\} + \{F_{\varepsilon^p}\}_{t-1} \quad (43)$$

where

$$\{F_{\varepsilon^p}\}_{t-1} = - \int_V [B]^T [D] \{\varepsilon^p\}_{t-1} dV \quad (44)$$

Here, $[B]$ is the strain–displacement matrix and $[D]$ is the elastic constitutive matrix.

Since the stiffness matrix remains constant throughout the analysis, its decomposition is performed only once, significantly reducing computational cost.

The strain field is updated using Cauchy relations:

$$\{\varepsilon\}_t = [B]\{u\}_t$$

Subsequently, plastic strain increments are computed, and stresses are updated accordingly. The yield surface is iteratively corrected until convergence is achieved, which is defined by:

$$\{d\varepsilon^p\}_t \leq \varepsilon_0$$

throughout the domain.

The proposed algorithm and corresponding computational implementation were validated against benchmark problems. In particular, the accuracy of numerical integration procedures was verified by evaluating stress distributions induced by the self-weight of a homogeneous soil layer.

Considering the specific operational conditions of pile foundations supporting storage tanks, the load-bearing capacity was experimentally evaluated through static load testing under axial compressive loading. The reaction system was formed by anchor piles installed along the same radial axis as the test pile and arranged symmetrically on both sides, ensuring balanced force distribution. During testing, neither the anchor piles nor the test pile were connected to the conductor block, thereby eliminating any unintended load-sharing effects and ensuring purely isolated loading conditions.

The anchor piles were interconnected by a rigid reaction system consisting of a thrust beam assembled from two I-section steel beams (No. 60). This structural configuration was designed to resist the reaction forces generated by the hydraulic jacks while maintaining sufficient stiffness. For a beam span of 3500 mm under a maximum applied load of 2000 kN, the mid-span deflection did not exceed 5 mm, corresponding to approximately 0.0014 of the span, which satisfies standard serviceability requirements for structural rigidity.

Static loading was applied using a hydraulic system comprising two DG-150 jacks, each with a rated capacity of 1500 kN, connected to an NSP-400 hydraulic power unit. The applied load was monitored using an MO-400 analog pressure gauge with a maximum capacity of 40 MPa and a resolution of 0.2 MPa. The jacks were mounted on a steel loading frame fixed to the pile head to ensure uniform and concentric load transfer throughout the testing process.

The reaction forces induced by the hydraulic jacks were transmitted through a system of rigid thrust beams specifically designed to minimize structural deformation and preserve geometric alignment during loading. The results of the static load tests, including load–settlement relationships, are summarized in the corresponding table and presented graphically in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Scheme of installations for static testing of piles
 1- anchor piles, 2 - distribution beams, 3 - over jack support beam, 4 - jack-1500-2000kN,
 5 - jack table, 6 - test pile, 7- reference system with deflection gauges

The results of the theoretical and experimental studies are presented in Figure 9

Figure 9. Dependence of pile settlement on the applied load

4. CONCLUSION

This study presents a comprehensive and refined methodology for analyzing the behavior of pile foundations under both dynamic and static vertical loading conditions, with particular relevance to offshore and critical infrastructure applications. The pile is modeled as a rigid stamp with a circular base on an elastic half-space, enabling the simulation of vertical vibrations and rotational oscillations, while also incorporating detailed analysis of axial load-bearing capacity and settlement behavior.

Analytical solutions for the governing equations of motion were derived to evaluate

harmonic oscillation amplitudes and dynamic displacement coefficients. The results show that pile foundations subjected to machinery- and wave-induced loads experience periodic vertical displacements, significantly influenced by pile mass and soil properties such as Poisson's ratio. Additionally, the combined effects of static and dynamic stresses beneath the pile base and surrounding soil were quantified.

The proposed numerical framework incorporates nonlinear soil behavior using plastic flow theory with hardening and Koiter's associated flow rule, implemented through an efficient axisymmetric finite element formulation. The developed incremental-iterative solution algorithm ensures computational stability and accuracy, as confirmed by strong agreement between numerical predictions and experimental results.

Overall, the findings highlight the critical role of soil nonlinearity and progressive shaft resistance mobilization in determining load-settlement response and bearing capacity. The developed methodology enables more accurate design calculations, contributing to optimized material use, reduced construction time, and improved cost-efficiency. It is particularly well-suited for the design and assessment of pile foundations in complex soil conditions, including offshore structures and load-sensitive facilities such as storage tanks.

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